

Introduction

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The Office for Science (OfS) in Garching (Germany) at the European Southern Observatory (ESO) organised the second edition of the Hypatia Colloquium Series. Announced for the first time in November 2020 [1], the Hypatia colloquia foresees a series of 20 min talks given by early career astronomers (up to 3 years from the PhD). In a few words, the Hypatia Colloquium Series is meant as a channel to allow excellent young researchers to show the results of their scientific work to a broad audience.

The call for applications for the 2022 Series was released in November 2021. ESO received almost 200 applications out of which an ad-hoc committee, composed by Fellows and staff astronomers both from ESO Germany and Chile, selected the 44 speakers of the new Series. The program was released in January 2022 and is available on the Hypatia pages*.

The programme page is meant as a resource to discover the scientific profile of the speakers. By clicking on the title of the talk, the visitor of the page has access to the abstract and the Curriculum Vitae of the speaker. Moreover, for each talk, we add a link to the YouTube video where the talk is recorded.

As done in the Hypatia 2021 book [1], we show on Figure 1 the distribution in terms of gender and year of PhD of the speakers of the Hypatia 2022 Series. We achieved a solid balance in terms of both gender and seniority of the speakers. Moreover, as can be appreciated in this booklet, the Series offers a fair coverage of most of the scientific research topics of modern astrophysics.

The Hypatia 2022 Series

The talks were scheduled on Tuesdays at 3pm Garching (Germany) time from January 18 to June 22, 2022 (except one week, when there was the ESO ASTRO2022 conference [2]). The format of this Series foresees two 20 min-long talks, each followed by questions and discussion. Most of the seminars were co-chaired by an ESO Student and an ESO Fellow.

The seminars were entirely hosted online using the video conferencing tool Zoom and live-streamed on the Hypatia Colloquium YouTube channel†. Attendees could register to the Series using a web form. Registered participants were able to attend the seminars and interact with the speakers via the Zoom meeting. Alternatively, the community was invited to attend the live events on the dedicated YouTube page. All YouTube attendees could ask questions during the live event using the Live Chat on YouTube or using a web form or by email if they preferred to not have a YouTube account. All the video recordings of the live events, including the content of the live chat, are available on the “Hypatia Colloquium 2022” playlist

accessible on the Hypatia YouTube page.

We show on Figure 2 the analytics of the Hypatia YouTube channel. In particular, the plot shows the number of views of the videos of the talks as a function of time for the year 2022. The numerous peaks of the views’ distribution corresponds to the time when the talks were broadcast live on YouTube. While the number of view does not exactly indicates the number of attendees of each event, on average each live event was followed by a total of 20 to 40 participants, with peaks of more than 60 participants.

Figure 1: Distribution in terms of gender and (expected) year of PhD completion (left and right plots, respectively) of the speakers of the Hypatia Colloquium Series.

The return to in-person events

We noted that the number of live attendees dropped towards the end of the series in June 2022. Starting with the months of March/April 2022, we witnessed a slow but constant return to the “normality” of our social and professional life. The number of congresses and workshops foreseeing an in-person participation flourished in 2022. Understandably, the drive to re-establish a contact with the astronomical community and colleagues via in-person meetings has affected the participation to online events. This might be particularly true for the youngest generation of astronomers who lived a very significant fraction of their young career under the severe circumstances imposed by the restrictions due to the COVID19 pandemic. Despite this, we are sure that with the Hypatia series, ESO has achieved the important goal to create a friendly and professional platform to allow the young generation of astronomers to show their scientific results. The booklet of proceedings and the collection of videos represent a snapshot of the astronomical research done today and a solid legacy for a predictably bright future of the speakers.

*<https://www.eso.org/sci/meetings/garching/hypatia-colloquium/program2022.html>

†<https://www.youtube.com/c/HypatiaColloquium>

Your videos got 3,878 views in 2022

Figure 2: Snapshot of the Hypatia YouTube channel analytics for the year 2022. The peaks of views correspond to the time when each event was broadcast live.

Supporting early career astronomers sustainably

Among its top values, ESO strives for excellence through innovation and to provide outstanding services to the community while fostering diversity and inclusion[‡]. In this context the ESO OfS maintains a number of programmes (e.g., Fellowship, Studentship, Early Career Visitor Programme) whose primary goal is to offer to early career scientists the opportunity to perform astronomical research in an enjoyable, professional and international environment. Along the same line, the Hypatia Colloquium Series was specifically designed to offer further support to the researchers at their early stages during a particularly challenging time (the COVID19 pandemic). In this context, online series of seminars, such as the Hypatia Colloquium one, was a valuable opportunity to maintain a solid level of scientific interaction within the community.

The reality of conferences and workshops in astronomy has recently returned to the in-person participation. While it is desirable that the near future will allow the community to maintain stable channels of communication and fruitful exchanges, the uncertainties related to the future impact of COVID19, the economical instability and the climate crisis call for a careful revision of the way the scientific community interacts. Moreover, the necessity of hosting scientific events able to include the most diverse plethora of attendees is a factor that should not

be ignored.

In this context, online events are an important resource to fulfill the described requirements in a sustainable way. It is a fact that some of the aspects of the in-person events (the most obvious being the possibility of unexpected encounters and the empathy implicit in the face-2-face discussions) are irreplaceable. Still, online events can and must be fully considered when planning an event. It is somehow clear that all the basic logic/scheme of a classic in-person meeting (a series of talks followed by questions) can not work for an online event. Hence, it is now important that researchers at all stages of career share their effort and creativity to design online meetings where the critical goals (e.g., foster productive discussions around major scientific questions, allow a fruitful interaction between senior astronomers and early career researchers) are not only preserved but possibly re-discovered as the core of our scientific life.

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References

- [1] Beccari, G., & Boffin, H.M.J., 2021, *The Messenger* 185, 23
- [2] Beccari, G., et al. 2022, *The Messenger* 187, 33

[‡]<https://www.eso.org/public/about-eso/vision-mission/>